

The Central Lava Tube Skylight in Mare Fecunditatis: Scientific Significance and Operational Advantages for Crewed Lunar Exploration. Long Xiao^{1,2}, Xingyang She², Weiyang Xu³. ¹ School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, China University of Geosciences (Wuhan), Wuhan, China, ² The State Key Laboratory of Lunar and Planetary Sciences, Macau University of Science and Technology, Macau, China. ³ Aerospace System Engineering Shanghai, Shanghai, China. Corresponding author: Longxiao@cug.edu.cn.

Introduction: Lunar lava tube skylights offer unparalleled scientific value: they provide direct access to pristine subsurface stratigraphy, recording the history of basaltic volcanism and crustal evolution, and their stable interior environments—shielded from radiation, micrometeorite impacts, and extreme temperature fluctuations—represent ideal natural shelters for long-term human outposts. Despite these merits, no crewed mission has ever explored a lava tube skylight. Here we advocate for the urgent investigation of the central lava tube skylight in Mare Fecunditatis. This feature stands out because of its exceptional location near the lunar equator (0.918° S, 48.659° E), which ensures favourable illumination and communication conditions. Most importantly, it possesses a unique sloping southeastern wall that provides natural access to the subsurface—a morphology not observed in any other known lunar skylight. In this study, we present its geological context, morphological characteristics, and high-resolution topographic and geochemical analyses, highlighting its scientific promise and operational feasibility.

Geological Background: Mare Fecunditatis is a ~310,000 km² low-latitude basalt plain on the lunar nearside (Chu et al., 2012), formed during the Pre-Nectarian period and subsequently filled by multiple phases of Imbrian and Eratosthenian mare basalts (Hiesinger et al., 2006). Unlike mascon basins, it exhibits marginal Bouguer gravity anomalies indicative of crustal thickness variation (Janle et al., 1981). The region hosts diverse volcanic and tectonic features, including sinuous rilles, domes, and skylights, recording a complex evolutionary history (Yue et al., 2025; Zhao et al., 2022).

Skylight Morphology: The central skylight is an elliptical pit ~10 m high and ~15 m deep (Wagner and Robinson 2014, 2022). High-resolution LRO NAC images (Fig. 1) reveal a gentle slope on its southeastern side, extending from the surface to the pit floor, with no overhangs or major structural disruptions. This slope distinguishes it from vertical pits elsewhere and could facilitate crewed descent and rover ingress.

Regional Topography and Geochemistry: Within a 100×100 km area centered on the skylight, SLDEM2015 data show gentle slopes (mean 3.16°, 0–2° dominant) and elevations from –3619 to –1049 m, indicating low topographic risk for landing and mobility (Fig. 2). Kaguya MI spectral mapping (Peters et al., 1994; Lemelin et al., 2019; Otake et al.,

2008, 2010, 2012) yields average FeO = 17.42 wt% and TiO₂ = 4.75 wt%, with distinct spatial variations that reflect multiple basaltic flow units. The skylight’s proximity to compositionally diverse basalts offers an opportunity to sample subsurface stratigraphy and constrain mantle evolution and eruption chronology (Fig. 3)

Conclusion: The Mare Fecunditatis skylight combines outstanding scientific potential—access to layered mare basalts recording volcanic history—with unique engineering advantages: equatorial location, benign regional topography, and a natural sloping entrance. It represents a high-priority target for future crewed missions aimed at both groundbreaking science and the establishment of sustainable lunar infrastructure.

Figure 1. (a) Location of Mare Fecunditatis on the Moon; red pentagram marks the skylight. (b) Detailed NAC view of the skylight, showing the southeastern slope.

Figure 2. (a) Kaguya TC image; (b) SLDEM2015 elevation; (c) Slope map (0–64°). Most terrain has slopes <2°.

Figure 3. Kaguya MI data: (a) false-color composite; (b) FeO (7.27–21.93 wt%); (c) TiO₂ (1.16–9.29 wt%).

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